

rated resistant, with means of 8-13% SS; Leuang 152 was highly resistant (no SS).

The correlation of incidence with yield was negatively linear except for CR1014. In 10 varieties, the regression coefficient was significant or highly significant (see table).

Yield loss ranged from -0.06% in

CR1014 to 1.1% in CR58-MRI538. Based on yield losses, susceptible entries could be tentatively classified for tolerance as follows:

Highly tolerant : CR1014,
(0-0.30%) Jagannath
Moderately tolerant : Sona, Padma
(0.31-0.60%)

Least tolerant : GEB24, Pankaj,
(0.61%–higher) CR94-MRI559,
Vijaya, Jaya,
CR58-MR1538,
Bala

As yield loss varied widely among varieties, economic injury and threshold levels also varied. □

Stem borers (SB) in dryland and wetland rice

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We compared SB infestation in an

irrigated wetland field planted to *indica* varieties and in a dryland field planted to *japonica* varieties. The experimental fields were planted the same day.

At 2 wk before harvest, 150 tillers/variety were dissected. SB infestation was higher in the japonica varieties (see figure). SB species found in

wetland indicas and dryland japonicas also differed.

Five SB sp. were collected in both rice environments: *Chilo suppressalis* (Walker), *C. auricilius* Dudgeon, *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker), *Maliarpha* sp., and *Sesamia inferens* (Walker). Species abundance in the indicas was *S. incertulas* > *C. auricilius* > *C. suppressalis* > *S. inferens* > *Maliarpha* sp. In the japonicas, it was *C. suppressalis* > *C. auricilius* > *S. inferens* > *Maliarpha* sp. > *S. incertulas*.

The indicas had fewer whiteheads (1-4%) and SB (4-12 larvae) than the japonicas (1-12% whiteheads and 0-130 SB larvae). Four Brazilian japonica varieties — Japones, Maranhao Vermelho, Manteiga, and Poupa Preguica — had the highest infestation. □

Species composition (%)

Stem borer larvae (no./150 tillers)

Whiteheads (%)

Relative abundance of rice SB in *japonica* varieties planted in dryland fields and *indica* varieties planted in wetland fields. IRRI farm, 1985 wet season.

Screening of rice accessions against leaf folder (LF) *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*

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We screened 32 rice accessions from the All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project for resistance to LF during 1986 wet season, using a seedling screening technique.

Pregenerated seeds of accessions were sown 6 cm apart in 6 rows in 50- × 40- × 10-cm wooden seedboxes. Each accession was planted across the width of the seedbox to maintain at least 5 hills (3 plants/hill)/row. One row of susceptible check TN1 and one row of resistant check Ptb 33 were sown at